

Survey paper on Products and Services Price Comparison

2021-2022

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Abstract— The Internet can make markets more competitive, but whether this holds for on-line price levels and price dispersion is unclear, perhaps because the maturity, or level of development. This paper explores how somebody can compare prices in terms of booking a hotel, electronics products, automobiles and used products etc. There are so many platforms who are providing price comparisons but that for a particular thing, for example goibibo providing the feature of comparing prices of hotels if someone is searching for hotels. This will provide the feature of comparing prices if you talk about hotel booking, electronic products, automobiles and used products etc. This application will help the user to avoid going to different platforms to compare prices of these things. In future this application can be upgradable that means user can be able to purchase products and services after price comparison through this application providing maximum benefit to the user in terms of efforts and prices. It will provide the consumer with the comparison of the product and services by crawling the different available websites. This application will be made using Python, Django, Sql, Html, CSS and flutter.

A. Keywords: online markets; price comparison sites; competition; price dispersion.

II. INTRODUCTION

This project is aimed at demonstrative price comparison website where people can compare prices of hotels, electronic products, automobiles, used products etc. They will also be able to read reviews from customers who have already compared similar products they are looking for. The purpose of this project is how a user can get more benefits with less efforts and can get the satisfied products and services.

These mobile apps enlist all the products, for which users are searching along with their prices that are running on different websites. For instance, if you are searching for a pair of shoes, then the shoes that you select will be displayed if it exists on the other sites as well with their price. So, you can easily compare the rates of shoes on Amazon with that of Walmart and Alibaba just at a single location. Interesting isn't it? Well, the aforementioned concept is actually very much appraised by today's generation reason being, it just makes shopping easy and cost-effective.

Plentiful businesses are looking for developing such apps and if you are one of them, here you will find out the top features of price comparison API India, architecture, the technology required, and everything else associated. Therefore, keep reading the post in order to grapple with a brief understanding of the development of the best and excelled price comparison app. When it comes to how to build a price comparison app there are a lot of things that you need to focus on. The first being the features that you would integrate into your application. Every shopper looks for the best deals & discounts before buying any product. Nowadays before purchasing anything the buyers do some online research of the products on the internet. One of the major factors which lead to purchasing of any product is cost or pricing. The buyers tend to compare prices before purchasing any product.

This price comparison website for products will help to compare the price from various e-commerce websites, This Price comparison site is extremely helpful for frequent online shoppers to check prices on different online stores in one place. This system will show you the product prices from different retailers to show you where to buy the product at affordable price, any two static websites classes are analyzed to get the pricing details, To get the pricing details, the system visits the website based on user's search and downloads the

html search page of that specific website, Once prices from both the websites are retrieved, it is displayed on our website in the form of price comparison. With price comparison software you can keep up with any changes in so many indicators that may worry you. This way you can accurately monitor the market factors that interest you most, including as many competitors as you require.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

As online shopping increases in popularity, PCSs have become one of the most important Web-based business intermediaries for both merchants and online shoppers [1]. Typically, comparison sites gather information on products and their prices imposed by different merchants, and enable online shoppers to select products and merchants to make purchase decisions in effective manners. In addition, owing to the large number of similar products and merchants on the Web, online shoppers may feel disoriented when facing the massive amount of information provided by a PCS. Indeed, conventional price-comparison agents help in determining “where to buy” a specific product; however, they do not appropriately support individual shoppers in determining “what to buy”. That is, it is generally assumed that online shoppers visit a PCS after determining to purchase a specific product. However, it is well known that the shopping process generally starts with the “what to buy” phase, where the shoppers determine specific products suitable for their customized needs. Therefore, traditional filtering and order-based PCSs are insufficient, and a more comprehensive and intelligent purchase-decision support is required.

- a) A similar related survey paper (Buaimin, 2012) stated that a web comparison site genuinely must return results with the low costs as what the users need yet exact outcomes additionally significant so users can get what they truly care about. It likewise relies upon how normal the data set is being refreshed any other way users will be confused when they analyzed it from other site. They have provided a solution as PriceWar.com where customers could track down the incredible deals on the home everyday food items. The best deals will be plainly featured. Despite the fact that not all customers are purchasing on the web, yet it is one of the ways of assisting shoppers with expanding their price awareness. Customers reserve the privilege to know whether the value they are seeing in the shops are great deals as it is guaranteed or not. Along these lines it is a benefit for the customers who are

consistently aware with regards to the current cost of a specific item so they are not cheated by the large words publicized by the shops. However this paper only focuses on groceries.

- b) Similar work (Passyn, 2013) pointed out that study was intended to acquire knowledge into online purchasers' actual use and reliance on item search

furthermore, value correlation sites. Other examination and measurable proof show that Shopbot use is arriving at its tipping point, in this way value uniqueness ought to be almost cleared. Nonetheless, a review of shopper solid products shows that huge value scattering endures.

- c) As the interest for the portable looking is expanding the need for a ton of secure, protected and solid managing is of most extreme interest. Cell phones, that became Associate in Nursing significant a piece of the present life, have decreased every one of the endeavours that square measure required for looking. There are 2 favours of it: first no got to substitute the line for an extended time frame in shopping centres just for examining the thing, second there'll be no extension for the fakes that occur in portable shopping. The exchanges which will follow oftentimes with the retailer's cloud will be made secure. the pattern of shopping on the web has returned to remain. Online shops are open 24 hours of the day and may be gotten to from wherever any place there's a web connection. the advantage and comfort of shopping on the web can constantly draw a ton of clients thereto. Notwithstanding, buyers should be ready and receptive to the dangers concerned and take extra consideration once looking on-line. Because of the receptiveness and battle of the net market, most business perpetually endeavour to keep up with the absolute best standard of safety yet as a client focused site to brighten up their business.

- d) The proposed framework looks at and shows the costs of an item from various web-based business sites. Top hunt results are shown to the client on a solitary point of interaction. Perception of item costs helps the client in deciding the best cost for an item. The framework diverts the client to the first site of a specific item, in the event that the client decides to purchase any item. The normal time taken by a client to physically look and look at cost of an item on various sites is over high, though the time taken by our framework to get the cost of item on similar sites is 5.8 seconds by and large. In this way, the client can get the best cost of an item inside 5 seconds. Additionally, the client gets advised with regards to the value drop of an intrigued item by the warning framework through email. Subsequently, our application saves time and burden caused to client

while looking and contrasting costs of items on the web.

- e) Information-intensive Web sites provide a wide access to a diverse range of information sources. However, the browsing behaviours of many users are not directed in that users do not focus on locating specific targets and often experience problems of information overload and uncertainty. In particular, novice users have a considerable difficulty making decisions based on information provided by such Web sites. Therefore, providing online users with useful information is a major challenge facing future Web environments.

IV. CONCLUSION

We addressed the problem of users going through multiple websites to search and compare the products and prices and solving this using our crawler application. It would provide the ease of searching products and services on best prices along with comparison of features, deals and shipping times. This application will provide the functionality of getting better buying options with minimum efforts by the user. This application will help the user to avoid going to different platforms to compare prices of these things.

In future this application can be upgradable that means user can be able to purchase products and services after price comparison through this application providing maximum benefit to the user in terms of efforts and prices.

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